

A New Method of Preparation of Solid Solutions of Calcium-Zinc Hydroxylapatites

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Manuscript received 16 August 1975; revised 8 October 1975; accepted 6 December 1975

The present work reports a successful attempt at the preparation of pure and homogeneous solid solutions of calcium-zinc hydroxylapatites over the entire compositional range by the method of co-precipitation in aqueous media.

CALCIUM hydroxylapatite (CaHA), $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$ is the chief constituent of human skeletal system¹. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic exchange reactions². $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Zn}^{2+}$ replacement in CaHA is of biological significance since it explains the mechanism of incorporation of zinc into human skeletal system. This exchange process results in the formation of a series of solid solutions of calcium-zinc hydroxylapatites according to the following equation.

Earlier methods of preparation of solid solutions of calcium-zinc hydroxylapatites by the solid state

reaction³ i.e., by firing mixtures containing various proportions of calcium and zinc hydroxylapatites at $\sim 1300^\circ$ were however found to be discontinuous and nonhomogeneous. The present work is an attempt to prepare samples of these homogeneous solid solutions on the entire compositional range by the method of co-precipitation in aqueous media.

Experimental

The chemicals used for the preparation of the samples were either A.R. (B.D.H.) or E. Merck (extra pure) grade. Stoichiometric quantities of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (solution A) and a solution containing Ca^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions in the proportion desired for the solid solution (solution B)

Fig. 1. X-ray diffraction spectra of Ca-Zn HA. (Spectra of sample nos. 1, 2, 4 and 7 of Table 1).

were prepared separately in carbondioxide free doubly distilled water and the pH of each of solution was scrupulously maintained above 11 by the addition of liquor ammonia. Then a part of the solution B was taken in a 2 l flask fitted with three holid rubber stopper carrying two separating funnels through two holes and a delivery tube through the third hole. Solution A and solution B were taken in the separating funnels and allowed to drop into the flask while the flask was kept at $37^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$ to stimulate biological conditions of the samples. The precipitation was carried out in carbondioxide free atmosphere and the medium of precipitation was stirred well by bubbling carbondioxide free air into the medium of precipitation through the delivery tube. The precipitate along with the mother liquor was aged by boiling under reflux for 30 min to improve homogeneity and crystallinity of the precipitate. The maintainance of the deserved pH during precipitation was ensured by resting the filtrate after separation of the precipitate since any alteration of pH of the medium during precipitation lead to the formation of calcium deficient apatites⁴. Samples

Results and Discussion

The results of the chemical analyses and molar volumes of the samples are given in Table 1. Based on the fact that a mole of each samples has a total 10 g atoms of Ca^{2+} and/or Zn^{2+} the molecular formulae of the samples were calculated from the results of chemical analysis. The observed value of molar gram atom ratio of 1.68 (Theoretical 1.67) of Ca/P

and Zn/P for the end members and $\frac{\text{Ca} + \text{Zn}}{\text{P}}$ for

others and their closeness of the values of molar volumes of the end members and those of the intermediate samples which lies within the range of the end members was to indicate the formation of homogeneous solid solutions⁷. The homogeneity and crystallinity of the samples were further confirmed by the values of lattice parameters of the samples.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Prof. G. Ferraras, University of Torino, Italy for X-ray data.

TABLE 1. CHEMICAL ANALYSES OF CALCIUM, ZINC HYDROXYLAPATITES AND THEIR SOLID SOLUTIONS

Sl. No.	Wt%			Molecular formulae	Molecular volume ml/mole	g. atomic ratio Ca + Zn/P	Lattice parameters (Å)	
	Ca	Zn	P				a	c
1	39.80	—	18.52	$\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	338.3	1.68	9.37	6.88
2	34.38	6.27	18.05	$\text{Ca}_9.0\text{Zn}_{1.0}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	342.3	1.67	9.26	6.73
3	26.79	16.64	17.31	$\text{Ca}_{7.2}\text{Zn}_{2.8}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	332.9	1.68	9.05	6.74
4	17.68	28.91	16.44	$\text{Ca}_6.0\text{Zn}_{4.0}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	330.0	1.67	8.84	6.62
5	10.15	38.74	15.80	$\text{Ca}_3.0\text{Zn}_{7.0}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	330.1	1.67	8.66	6.52
6	3.71	48.42	15.18	$\text{Ca}_{1.0}\text{Zn}_{9.0}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	325.0	1.67	8.45	6.47
7	—	52.10	14.77	$\text{Zn}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	326.7	1.68	8.26	6.43

dried at 100° for few hr were analysed complexometrically^{5,6} and their molar volumes were determined by using a specific gravity bottle and toluene as a solvent⁷. In the X-ray diffraction patterns of powdered samples were obtained with a Nerelec powder diffractometer employing CuK_α radiation (Ni-filtered radiation). Sharp peaks separated by less than 0.1 (degree 2θ) can be resolved with a 0.006 inch entrance slit at a scan rate of 1 degree 2θ per min using tube voltage and current of 50 KV and 20 mA respectively. The d spacings and the corresponding a and c parameter values are calculated by the well established method of Azaroff⁸ and from them the unit cell volumes of the samples are calculated and given in Table 1. The X-ray diffraction patterns of a representative set of the samples (S. No. 1, 2, 4 and 7 of Table 1) are given in Fig. 1.

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